

DETERMINATION OF MELATONIN HORMONE STATUS IN WOMEN WITH POLYCYSTIC OVARIES AND OBESITY OF FERTILE AGE

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Abstract. Today, influence of the melatonin hormone on the gonadotropic function of the pituitary gland and the process of ovariogenesis is widely studied as a new direction in the study of reproductive problems of obese women. In addition obesity, which is a comorbidity of polycystic ovary syndrome, and its correlation with melatonin secretion are of interest to many people today. In this article, we talked about the importance of the problem mentioned above.

Key words : polycystic ovary syndrome, melatonin, obesity

Relevance of the topic. Today, the influence of the melatonin hormone on the gonadotropic function of the pituitary gland and the process of ovariogenesis is widely studied as a new direction in the study of reproductive problems of obese women. In addition, obesity, which is noted as a concomitant disease in polycystic ovary syndrome, and its correlation with melatonin secretion are of interest to many people today. According to the data of the world health organization between 1980 and 2013, qualitatively, the body mass index of people above 25 is from 29.8% to 38% among women, and from 28.8% to 36.9% among men. We can see that it has increased to %.

It is known that obesity is a chronic disease that is now recognized as a "social pandemic", caused by genetic factors, metabolic disorders and lifestyle, and leads to many serious complications and death. Can also lead to lim. Android-type obesity in women causes a number of diseases and clinical conditions in them.

The purpose of the study: to study the sleep disorders in women of fertile age suffering from obesity and the effect of this condition on the ovarian dysfunction and the concentration of the melatonin hormone in the blood.

Research material and method: 27 women aged 18-36 years with a body mass index greater than 25 with various forms of menstrual cycle disorders and 33 women with a normal body weight for comparison, was obtained for a control group of women without menstrual cycle disturbances. As research methods, anamnestic data, the amount of melatonin in saliva, and the concentration of 6-sulfoxymelatonin in urine, which is the first metabolite of melatonin, were examined.

The results obtained. Sleep disorders were noted in 13 (48%) of obese women (n=27) taken for examination. In addition, sleep apnea was noted in 8 of them. When the melatonin concentration in the saliva of the control group and the control group was checked, the average results were 13.2 and 24.7 pg/ml, respectively. The average amount of 6-sulfoxymelatonin in urine was 15.1 and 29.3 pg/ml, respectively.

Conclusion. Based on the results of the research, it can be concluded that women of fertile age with body mass index above 25 are more likely to experience various forms of sleep disorders and menstrual cycle disorders. At the same time, it can be observed that in such women, the amount of melatonin in the blood and the amount of 6-sulfoxymelatonin in the urine are significantly reduced compared to women with a normal body weight.

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